

COMPLAINTS AFTER INTESTINAL INFECTIONS IN YOUNG CHILDREN IN THE 6 MO LONG CATAMNESIS AND LOOKING FOR THEIR PATHOGENETIC MECHANISMS

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The aim. Evaluate parents' complaints of their children's intestinal health during the first 6 months after bacterial enterocolitis or rotavirus gastroenteritis by direct interview and comparison of the resulting follow-up with the coprological indicators at the peak of the infectious process.

Materials and methods. The study involved 29 children aged from 6 to 24 months with acute diarrhea, who was hospitalized at the children's hospital. Patients were divided into 2 groups. The first (I) study group included 18 patients with acute bacterial enterocolitis (ICD: A02, A04), which was caused by *Kampilobacter jejuni*, *Salmonella enteritidis*, *Yersinia enterocolitica*, and enteropathogenic *Escherichia coli*. The second (II) group consisted of 11 children with rotavirus gastroenteritis (ICD A08.0). All children underwent coprological tests, which included examination of the reducing substances, calprotectin, fecal content of short-chain fatty acids, and lactate acid.

Results and discussion. The study found that more than half (55%) of children in the follow-up during the first 6 months had intestinal disorders. The most common complaint was the loose stool, which in 5 (17%) children corresponded to chronic functional diarrhea G5 according to Roman criteria IV. Comparing the complaints of the recidivated abdominal pain («colic») in group I there was a significantly more frequent incident (13 of 18 children) than in group II (3 of 11, OR=6.1 95% CI 1.1-33.2, p=0.04). Similarly, first group children had slightly more frequent complaints of temporary thinning of the stool (13 of 18) compared with the frequency of disorders in group II (5 of 11, OR=3.1 95% CI 0.6-15.0, p=0.16).

There were no significant correlations between the frequency of complaints in the follow-up and the degree of coprological abnormalities at the height of the infectious process. Post-infectious disorders, both after viral and bacterial diarrhea, are formed regardless of the intensity of the acute inflammation, carbohydrate hydrolysis disorders, and disorders of metabolic activity of the intestinal microbiome. They are

most likely related to the development of low-grade intestinal inflammation and/or pathogenic «CNS-intestinal» connections.

Conclusion. Stool disorders and recurrent abdominal pain during bowel recovery in children after acute infectious diarrheas occur in more than half of children within the next 6 months after discharge from the hospital and require the elaboration of more treatment.